

Security debt and security vulnerability relationship groups

Defining Security Debt: A Case Study Based On Practice

Group #	Difference between SD and security vulnerabilities (SDSV)	# of respondents
SDSV1	Security vulnerabilities reflect the current status and SD is postponed issues	10
SDSV3	SD and security vulnerabilities are the same	9
SDSV6	Security vulnerabilities are a subset of SD	8
SDSV5	Postponed security vulnerabilities become SD	5
SDSV2	Security vulnerabilities are easy to fix and SD is not easy to fix	2
SDSV4	SD can lead to security vulnerabilities	1